

Non-Gaussianities from a kinetic pre-inflationary universe

Master of Advanced Studies in Physics

Y. L. Launay

*University of Cambridge, Cambridge CB3 0WA, United Kingdom**

Supervised by W. J. Handley

Astrophysics Group, Cavendish Laboratory, J.J. Thomson Avenue, Cambridge, CB3 0HE, United Kingdom and Kavli Institute for Cosmology, Madingley Road, Cambridge, CB3 0HA, United Kingdom

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Modern inflation theory is based on Mukhanov-Sasaki equations which give a perturbative framework to propagate initial quantum fluctuations as sources of the Cosmic Microwave Background (CMB) anisotropies encountered at the recombination epoch. Following previous work on initial conditions for the power spectrum, this work extends the kinetic pre-inflation model to the derivation of the primordial bispectrum, related to 3-point correlations. We derive here the slow-roll era contributions to the bispectrum thanks to the In-In formalism for different initial conditions. In addition to an oscillating locally-shaped bispectrum, it is found that the dependence on the time and nature of the transition between pre-inflation and inflation is strong. As a main result, new UV and IR divergences are encountered for the non-Gaussianities, showed to be independent of the choice of the vacuum. Finally, the validity of the calculus is tackled in an EFT framework and paves the way for conclusions on further needed work.

I. INTRODUCTION

Today's main cosmological model is carried by an accumulation of valuable data-constrained models, allowing us to quantify all cosmological parameters thanks to diversified observables such as the CMB, BAO, Supernovae, and galaxy clusters counts [1, 2]. As a non-negligible strength, extremely specific pipelines have allowed the community to account for systematics that can be trusted.

However, for a few years, experimental incoherence and tensions have remained statistically persistent among these results. Despite the latest surveys agreeing with their historic counterparts on the constitution of the universe (density parameters), other parameters inferred from multi-sourced data (supernovae measurements [3] and large-scale structure surveys [4–7]) have been recently confirmed without statistical matching. The community is therefore inheriting challenging tensions [8–10] such as those of the Hubble constant or the curvature parameter, highlighting the need for improved modeling of, respectively, the expansion rate or the shape of the universe. An experimental warning is the most reliable call for a change, and theorists [11] came to the same conclusions regarding these tensions and attributed the source of error to the modeling of physics, systematics, or presumably a mix of both. Many questions remain unanswered in cosmology.

In the last decade, insights have been made at the Kavli Institute for Cosmology Cambridge (KICC) in the group led by A. Lasenby, M. Hobson, and W. Handley. Following the work of Will Handley [12], the group not only ex-

posed [13] the possibility of a pre-inflation era dominated by the kinetic term sourcing the following slow-roll inflation but also successfully tested it against Planck 2018 CMB data [6, 14, 15] alongside new initial conditions parameterising the inflation.

While inflation was proposed to explain the initial conditions of the universe [16]—its extreme flatness and the Horizon problem—it also led to many supplementary predictions, especially the non-Gaussianity of the power spectrum [17], or the necessity of higher order correlation functions to describe the primordial cosmological fluid distribution. This description can be made thanks to the bispectrum [17], the spectrum of triangular space correlations. As the experiments and estimators recently gave their first conclusions on the existence of non-Gaussianities in the CMB map [18–20], and so the first reconstructions of the bispectrum, it is then essential to evaluate the non-Gaussianities of this new model issued from kinetic dominance. To be able to compete with hundreds of other inflationary model, this is the minimal requirement.

Within this context, this article is structured as follows: before defining the bispectrum, section II gives a brief reminder of the key equations for both the background and perturbed physics of the early universe as provided by the Friedmann-Lemaître formalism as much as those of the Mukhanov Sasaki equations. Section III contains the summary of the full derivation of the chosen bispectrum model for this new inflationary universe. Its analysis leads to a further study of the asymptotic divergences of the non-Gaussianities depending on the choice of the initial conditions for inflation. Finally, section IV analyses the encountered new UV-IR divergences and brings transparency on the validity and exhaustivity of our calculus.

In this article, $8\pi G = c = \hbar = 1$ units are used.

* yoann.launay@outlook.com

II. THEORY OF BACKGROUND COSMOLOGY AND PERTURBATIVE FORMALISM

A. Inflation background equations

Inflation theory assumes the existence of a dominating single scalar field: the inflaton ϕ . It constitutes a parametrization of the time-evolution of the energy density, reflected in the choice of the Einstein-Hilbert action associated with the inflaton in a potential V

$$S = \int d^4x \sqrt{|g|} \left[\frac{1}{2}R + \frac{1}{2}g^{\mu\nu} \partial_\mu \phi \partial_\nu \phi - V(\phi) \right], \quad (1)$$

where g is the space-time metric and R is the Ricci scalar (General Relativity action term). This quantity simplifies greatly when assuming a homogeneous ($\nabla\phi = \vec{0}$), flat and expanding early universe (scale factor a) and, by applying the least action principle, gives the standard equations of inflation for the FLRW metric

$$\begin{cases} \frac{d^2\phi}{dt^2} + 3H \frac{d\phi}{dt} + \frac{dV}{d\phi} = 0 \\ \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{d\phi}{dt} \right)^2 + V(\phi) = 3H^2, \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where $H = \frac{d \ln a}{dt}$ is the Hubble parameter in time. In the past, the study [21] of these equations lead to two main types of solutions: slow-roll (SR) inflation where $(\frac{d\phi}{dt})^2 \ll V(\phi)$ and Kinetic Dominance (KD) inflation where $(\frac{d\phi}{dt})^2 \gg V(\phi)$. One can understand the inflation process as a common Newtonian well where potential and kinetic terms are converted into each other depending on time and metrics.

The KD epoch is most likely to happen before the SR one [21], setting the KD period as a pre-inflation. After this, a usual SR inflation would occur with constant friction H so that the universe exponentially expands until the end of inflation, just before the start of the classical Big-Bang era (see Fig. 1).

The following expressions [21] correspond to a Kinetic Dominated (KD) inflation without auxiliary fluids, where the conformal time $\eta = 0$ (with the equivalence $\eta(t) = \int_0^t \frac{dt'}{a(t')}$) is set as the end of the KD inflation and η_t the time of the end of the slow-roll inflation (see Fig. 1) where the maximum scale of the Hubble radius reached, so that

$$\begin{aligned} a(\eta) &\propto \left(1 + \frac{2\eta}{\eta_t}\right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \\ H(\eta) &= H_t \left(1 + \frac{2\eta}{\eta_t}\right)^{-\frac{3}{2}}, \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

This formalism reminds us that the KD universe has a singularity in a finite conformal past at $-\eta_t/2$.

On the other hand, the slow-roll inflation (characterized by $\epsilon = -\frac{\dot{H}}{H^2} \ll 1$), assumed constant, is nearly a De Sitter configuration for simplicity [22]

$$\begin{aligned} a(\eta) &\propto \frac{1}{H_t(\eta_t - \eta)} \\ H(\eta) &= H_t, \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

In this work, the slow-roll parameter ϵ is set as 0.01, a consistent value following the experimental constraints on the spectral index n_s [6] and the value of H_t is arbitrarily chosen to be 1.

B. Quadratic perturbations of the metric

In the case of inflation, one can consider independently scalar (ψ , Φ , B), vector (N^V , C) and tensorial (h) perturbations of the FLRW metric summarized in the SVT decomposition [23]

$$\begin{cases} ds^2 = (1 + 2\Phi)dt^2 - 2aB_i dx^i dt \\ \quad - a^2((1 - 2\psi)\delta_{ij} + E_{ij})dx^i dx^j \\ B_i = \partial_i B + N_i^V \\ E_{ij} = h_{ij} + 2\partial_{ij}E + \partial_i C_j, \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

given by the inflaton perturbation $\delta\phi(t, \vec{x}) = \phi(t, \vec{x}) - \bar{\phi}(t)$, $\bar{\phi}(t)$ being the background inflaton, i.e. following eq. 2. However, differential geometry allows to change freely the definition of the perturbation by changing the coordinates: this is the gauge choice. Physical quantities can then only be gauge invariants. The well-known comoving curvature perturbation is one of them and writes for instance in the ($\delta\phi = 0$)-gauge as [24]

$$\zeta = \psi + H\delta\phi/\dot{\bar{\phi}} = \psi, \quad (6)$$

In the following, only scalar perturbations are considered but a similar work could be done with VT modes. The first-order perturbations appear explicitly in the action (1) when injecting eq. 5 and simplifying with the background equations. Applying the least action principle finally gives the Mukhanov-Sasaki equations [24, 25] which write in Fourier space as

$$\begin{cases} v_k'' + (k^2 - \frac{z''}{z})v_k = 0 \\ v_k = z\zeta_k \\ z = \frac{a}{H} \frac{d\bar{\phi}}{dt}, \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

where $v_k(t) = \int \frac{d^3x}{(2\pi)^3} v(t, \vec{x}) e^{i\vec{k}\cdot\vec{x}}$.

Once spacetime boundary conditions and the background are chosen, these equations allow us to describe all perturbations during inflation in both KD and SR inflations. Each mode k corresponds to a monochromatic perturbation of the spatial comoving curvature.

Once the background is chosen through z , one has all elements to solve the Mukhanov-Sasaki equations. Solutions have been found for the sequence of kinetic dominance and slow-roll inflation, using a continuous junction [14, 26] as Fig 1 illustrates. From now on, this modulation of inflation will be assumed and we will refer to pre-inflation and inflation as KD and SR epochs of the KD-SR inflation.

The general form of the KD solution for ζ_k is

$$u_k^{\text{KD}} = \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{\frac{k\eta_t}{\epsilon}} \left[A_k H_0^{(1)}(k(\eta + \frac{\eta_t}{2})) + B_k H_0^{(2)}(k(\eta + \frac{\eta_t}{2})) \right], \quad (8)$$

where $H_n^{(i)}$ designates the n^{th} -order Hankel function of type i . A_k and B_k coefficients contain the vacuum initial condition which is set at the deepest in the horizon [14, 26], i.e. at the end of this era ($\eta = 0^-$, see 2 on Fig. 1) when the influenced comoving scales are numerous.

On the other hand, the general solution for the SR ζ_k modes is

$$u_k^{\text{SR}}(\eta) = \frac{i}{\eta_t k \sqrt{2\epsilon}} \left[C_k e^{-ik(\eta-\eta_t)} (1 + ik(\eta-\eta_t)) - D_k e^{+ik(\eta-\eta_t)} (1 - ik(\eta-\eta_t)) \right], \quad (9)$$

The mathematical smooth junction between the KD epoch ($\eta \leq 0^-$) and the SR solution ($\eta \geq 0^+$) is realized at $\eta = 0$ and ensures initial conditions for the latter. η_t is then the conformal time at which inflation ends. About C_k and D_k coefficients, they depend on A_k and B_k ones and are essentially Bogolyubov parameters for the choice of the vacuum [27]. This equivalently means an excited state built upon BD vacuum. Tab. II shows these different approaches that will be used in the following for the imprint of the pre-inflation vacuum on the initial conditions (IC) of the slow-roll inflation (C_k and D_k coefficients).

C. Cubic perturbations of the metric

As no solutions can be derived easily from eq. 1 at cubic order, the latter terms will be considered as perturbations of the Mukhanov-Sasaki solutions and corrections will be added to them through In-In formalism [28] in the next section. From the integrated Lagrangian in this equation, one derives the Hamiltonian perturbation at cubic order in ζ and its partial derivatives [22]. As a simple model, boundary terms of the Hamiltonian are neglected by assuming a constant slow-roll parameter (see eq. (4.37) in [22], ' η' ' parameter set as 0). The cosmological fluid is set with a constant sound velocity $c_s = 1$. As the reader may have noticed, it doesn't call for any $P(X, \phi)$ theories and is the simplest inflationary model. The cubic contributions write

$$H_{\text{int}}(t) = \int -a^3 \epsilon^2 \zeta \dot{\zeta}^2 - a \epsilon^2 \zeta (\nabla \zeta)^2 + 2a \epsilon \dot{\zeta} (\nabla \zeta) (\nabla \chi) - \frac{\epsilon}{2a} (\partial_i \zeta) (\partial^i \chi) \nabla^2 \chi - \frac{\epsilon}{4a} \nabla^2 \zeta (\nabla \chi)^2 d^3 x, \quad (10)$$

with $\partial^2 \chi = \epsilon a^2 \dot{\zeta}$. We number these contributions from 1 to 5 in this order. Each contribution to the Hamiltonian will constitute, after summing, a contribution to the bispectrum according to the In-In formalism at first order [22]. For further studies to improve the magnitude of non-Gaussianities, we recommend the use of non-perfect cosmological fluids and multi-fluids that have been left out of the scope of this work.

FIG. 1. Slow-roll finite inflation approach over time to answer the causalities of the CMB epoch, which has a given fluctuation scale (black dashed line) delimiting the so-called 'Horizon'. Quantum fluctuations give major contributions to the comoving curvature on the colored zone before freezing. 1) Pre-inflation starts and is dominated by the kinetics of the inflaton. 2) The transition to slow-roll inflation occurs and the spatial comoving curvature is perturbed from rest by initial quantum fluctuations. 3) The slow-roll inflation begins in an approximate De Sitter universe with an exponential expansion. 4) The Hubble radius decreases and exits the horizon. The inflation slows down and the Hubble radius variation turns around. 5) The Hubble radius increases and re-enters the horizon. The comoving curvature varies again starting from its value at horizon exit. 6) After 380,000 years, photons and matter decouple and the CMB has the imprint of the power spectrum of the propagated comoving curvature. Classical slow-roll inflation would have an infinite and straight slow-roll inflation to the far past (red dashed line).

D. From the spectrum to the bispectrum

Once the Fourier modes v_k are known and so the ζ_k , one deduces their value at horizon exit (step 4 in Fig. 1), which remain the same as before re-entry (step 5 in Fig. 1) because the perturbations freeze if not in the horizon.

In Figure 1 at step 5, and without knowing the content of epochs 4 to 5, one knows the primordial comoving curvature perturbation responsible for the fluctuation scale of the CMB (by transferring from 5 to 6 with a transfer function [?]) that we can see through its scalar power spectrum Δ_ζ

$$\begin{cases} \langle \zeta_{\vec{k}} \zeta_{\vec{k}'} \rangle = (2\pi)^3 \delta(\vec{k} + \vec{k}') P_\zeta(k) \\ \Delta_\zeta(k) = \frac{k^3}{2\pi^2} P_\zeta(k), \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

It is the power spectrum of the primordial 2-points space correlation function. In particular, the spectrum of the KD-SR model writes [26]

$$\Delta_\zeta(k) = \frac{H_t^2 k}{4\epsilon \pi^2} |C_k - D_k|^2, \quad (12)$$

Fig. 2 shows this spectrum for different initial conditions. The link between inflation, a theory for the

FIG. 2. Scalar power spectrum for different quantum initial conditions. ϵ and H_t are equal to 1 without loss of generality.

early universe, and a modern observable that we can indirectly measure is thereby established. In the past [13, 14, 21], the different inflation models have been successfully tested against this data. Being able to distinguish properly which IC gives the best fit to the data is an unsolved problem [14] which could be solved by new datasets (e.g. Simons Observatory's).

However, in addition to a set of indistinguishable initial conditions [14], the scalar power spectrum (2-point correlations) doesn't account for all the information needed to describe the primordial space distribution. Non-Gaussianities can occur and call for higher-order studies by using more than two-point correlation functions. Many types of inflation models made this prediction [17] and data confirmed it [18]. This is why the study of the scalar bispectrum B is relevant as it is defined as the spectrum of the three-point correlation function (3-PCF)

$$\langle \zeta_{\vec{k}_1} \zeta_{\vec{k}_2} \zeta_{\vec{k}_3} \rangle = (2\pi)^3 \delta^{(3)}(\vec{k}_1 + \vec{k}_2 + \vec{k}_3) B_\zeta(k_1, k_2, k_3), \quad (13)$$

B is then only defined on the triangles made of the Fourier vector modes. This will be kept implicit in the following. Statistical isotropy is assumed for the triangles which explains that the parameters of B are only the magnitudes of the vectors. It is possible to change variables and use natural triangular slices as suggested by the community [19]. The triangle lies at a distance $2k/\sqrt{3}$ in the plane orthogonal to the direction $(1, 1, 1)$ and has a side α (see Fig. 3) and an associated height β so that

$$\begin{cases} k_1 = k(1 - \beta) \\ k_2 = k(1 + \alpha + \beta)/2 \\ k_3 = k(1 - \alpha + \beta)/2 \\ k = (k_1 + k_2 + k_3)/2 \\ \text{with } 0 \leq \beta \leq 1 \text{ and } -(1 - \beta) \leq \alpha \leq 1 - \beta, \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

Associated with this observable, two other quantities are of great importance to studying geometry and the

FIG. 3. Region of definition of the bispectrum (yellow volume) delimited by red lines ($k_1 = k_2, k_3 = 0$; $k_2 = k_3, k_1 = 0$; $k_3 = k_1, k_2 = 0$) between which $k_1 + k_2 + k_3 = 0$ (ie a triangle with sides k_1, k_2 and k_3 is possible). The triangular slices parametrization uses the green equilateral triangle, the center of which is at distance k to the origin. Figures and methods come from [19].

magnitude of non-Gaussianities. The dimensionless-shape function is defined as the angular integrand of the 3-PCF

$$\mathcal{S}(k_1, k_2, k_3) = (k_1 k_2 k_3)^2 \mathcal{B}(k_1, k_2, k_3), \quad (15)$$

whereas the non-Gaussianity magnitude is usually studied through the so-called reduced bispectrum

$$f_{\text{NL}}(k_1, k_2, k_3) = \frac{5}{6} \frac{B(k_1, k_2, k_3)}{\mathcal{P}(k_1)\mathcal{P}(k_2) + \mathcal{P}(k_1)\mathcal{P}(k_3) + \mathcal{P}(k_2)\mathcal{P}(k_3)}, \quad (16)$$

where $\frac{3}{5}f_{\text{NL}}$ is by convention the magnitude of the quadratic deviation from a Gaussian model for ζ [22]. The first constraints on this amplitude usually referred to as $f_{\text{NL}}^{\text{local}}$, have been set with Planck 2018 mission [18]. Other orthogonal patterns of reduced bispectrums are not studied here.

III. KD-SOURCED SLOW-ROLL INFLATION

A. In-In bispectrum model

Following In-In formalism [28], the bispectrum at t is the mean value of the quantum observable $\widehat{O}(t) = \widehat{\zeta}_{k_1}(t)\widehat{\zeta}_{k_2}(t)\widehat{\zeta}_{k_3}(t)$ associated to the quantum interacting vacuum (*in* state) at the same time

$$\langle \widehat{O}(t) \rangle = \frac{\langle in | \widehat{O}(t) | in \rangle}{\langle in | in \rangle}, \quad (17)$$

However, computing this value within QFT demands the in-state in terms of operators and the vacuum of the free Hamiltonian only. This can be done with a mathematical trick; by writing the evolving Hamiltonian diagonalization of the in-state

$$|in(t^*)\rangle = \sum_n \langle n | in(t_1) \rangle e^{-iE_n(t^* - t_1)} |n\rangle, \quad (18)$$

one can access the free vacuum $|0\rangle$ by setting $t^* = -\infty(1 + i\delta) = -\infty^+$ where $i\delta$ is a small deviation from the real plan. In fact, since $E_0 = 0$, terms vanish except the vacuum one and so $|in(-\infty^+)\rangle \propto |0\rangle$. Then the in-state at t is obtained by applying the usual evolution operator from time $-\infty^+$ to t .

In the case of KD-SR inflation, there is a singularity in both a cosmological and conformal finite past. It means that it is impossible to reach the vacuum with the previous mathematical trick in the far past.

This was already a problem when imposing the IC for the scalar spectrum in Contaldi's approach [26]: it was impossible to make an initial condition of it at the singularity where solutions for Mukhanov-Sasaki equations vanish [14]. This problem was solved by imposing the initial condition at the transition from KD to SR, where the influence of the interacting vacuum is maximum. This choice of the origin of phases is an open problem but still, spectrum models with late-imposed vacua can be consistent with Planck data and not distinguishable from other vacua in the power spectrum [14].

In terms of In-In formalism, it is equivalent to start the calculus with $|in(t_{tr})\rangle = |0\rangle$, where t_{tr} is the time at which the regime transition is made.

From there, the time-ordered evolution operator gives the "in" state at time t

$$\begin{aligned} |in\rangle &= U(t, t_{tr}) |\Omega(t_{tr})\rangle \\ &= T \exp(-i \int_{t_{tr}}^t H_{int}(t') dt') |0\rangle, \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

Using it at first order in eq. 17, we have the formula for the bispectrum in conformal time

$$B(k_1, k_2, k_3) = 2Im \left[\langle 0 | \widehat{O}_{k_1 k_2 k_3}(\eta_t) \int_{\eta_{tr}}^{\eta_t} \widehat{H}_{int}(\eta) a(\eta) d\eta | 0 \rangle \right], \quad (20)$$

where $\eta_{tr} = 0$ is the conformal time of KD-SR transition whereas it is $\eta_{tr} = -\infty^+$ for usual SR inflation [22, 28].

To make these terms explicit, a quantification of the modes is required, supported by the solutions of the Mukhanov-Sasaki equations in eq. 9

$$\begin{cases} \hat{\zeta}_k &= \hat{\zeta}_k^+ + \hat{\zeta}_k^- = u_k \hat{a}_k + u_{-k}^* \hat{a}_{-k}^\dagger \\ [\hat{a}_{k_1}, \hat{a}_{k_2}^\dagger] &= (2\pi)^3 \delta^{(3)}(\vec{k}_1 + \vec{k}_2), \end{cases} \quad (21)$$

where \hat{a}_k and \hat{a}_k^\dagger are the annihilation and creation operators associated with the cosmological background quantified problem. Once the Hamiltonian has been quantified through ζ (see Appendix A), Wick's theorem allows us to write for each contribution of eq. 10 the expression of $B_{1,2,3,4,5}$ in the form

$$\begin{aligned} B_i &= 2\lambda_i f_i(\vec{k}_1, \vec{k}_2, \vec{k}_3) \times \\ &Im \left[u_{k_1}(\eta_t) u_{k_2}(\eta_t) u_{k_3}(\eta_t) G_{l,m,n}^q(k_1, k_2, k_3) \right] \\ &+ 5 \text{ permutations} \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

where $u = u^{SR}$ is that of eq. 9 and with

$$G_{l,m,n}^q(k_1, k_2, k_3, \eta_t) = \int_{\eta_0}^{\eta_t} a(\eta)^{1+q-l-m-n} \frac{d^l u_{k_1}^*(\eta)}{d\eta^l} \frac{d^m u_{k_2}^*(\eta)}{d\eta^m} \frac{d^n u_{k_3}^*(\eta)}{d\eta^n} d\eta, \quad (23)$$

where the λ_i and f_i are defined in Tab. I. Despite this formalism being convenient, the five contributions only need the analytic form of G_{000}^1 and G_{011}^3 , the (lmn) permutations being $(k_1 k_2 k_3)$ -ones: eg. $G_{110}^3(k_1, k_2, k_3) = G_{011}^3(k_3, k_1, k_2)$, etc (see Appendix B for more details).

It should also be noted that the dependence on quantum initial conditions lie in $G_{l,m,n}^q$ where C_k and D_k coefficients are. By linearity, each contribution can now be computed.

The next section will then tackle the calculus of these bispectrum integrals.

B. Observables derivation

As a tool for comparison of the next results, we remind in Appendix C the contributions for usual slow-roll inflation without kinetic dominance [22]. For this case of classical inflation with constant ϵ and $c_s = 1$, non-Gaussianity on non-squeezed triangles are small but existing.

Unlike this classical inflation calculation, interference appears with C_k and D_k coefficients between two competing terms: $+ik\eta$ and $-ik\eta$ waves. This reduces the direct access to the observables. In this section, only a summary of the theoretical results is provided, relying on Tab. IV for more details about the different auxiliary functions that have been computed and used.

To deal with eq. 22, the explicit calculus of each contribution is based on the following formalism

$$\begin{cases} Im [u_{k_1}(\eta_t) u_{k_2}(\eta_t) u_{k_3}(\eta_t) G_{011}^3(k_1, k_2, k_3, \eta_t)] \\ \quad = \frac{H_t^4}{8\epsilon^3} \frac{1}{k_1^2} \mathcal{S}_R(k_1, k_2, k_3, \eta_t) \\ Im [u_{k_1}(\eta_t) u_{k_2}(\eta_t) u_{k_3}(\eta_t) G_{000}^1(k_1, k_2, k_3, \eta_t)] \\ \quad = \frac{H_t^4}{8\epsilon^3} \frac{1}{k_1^2 k_2^2 k_3^2} [\mathcal{S}_F(k_1, k_2, k_3, \eta_t) + \mathcal{S}_I(k_1, k_2, k_3, \eta_t)], \end{cases} \quad (24)$$

where auxiliary functions R , F and I are integrated interference terms lying in G functions. \mathcal{S} is the functional summing weighted interference terms

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{S}_{Func}(k_1, k_2, k_3, \eta_t) &= \\ Im \{ \sum_{(Q_{k_1}, Q_{k_2}, Q_{k_3}) \in \{C_k, -D_k\}^3} Q_{k_1} Q_{k_2} Q_{k_3} \\ &\quad \sum_{(P_{k_1}, P_{k_2}, P_{k_3}) \in \{C_k, -D_k\}^3} P_{k_1}^* P_{k_2}^* P_{k_3}^* \\ &Func(\alpha(P_{k_1}), \alpha(P_{k_2}), \alpha(P_{k_3}), k_1, k_2, k_3, \eta_t) \}, \end{aligned} \quad (25)$$

All of these functions are explicitly computed in Tab. IV and are difficult to condense into one simple and short formula. Indeed, despite G_{011}^3 or R functions being convergent, this is not the case of G_{000}^1 at first sight. This is because its I part is divergent if we don't look at the

TABLE I. Main cubic contributions of the bispectrum, the associated scalings, and In-In integrals.

$B(k_1, k_2, k_3)$	H_{int}	λ	$f(k_1, k_2, k_3)$	$G_{lmn}^q(k_1, k_2, k_3)$
B_1	$-a^3 \epsilon^2 \zeta^2$	$-\epsilon^2$	1	G_{011}^3
B_2	$-a\epsilon^2 \zeta (\nabla \zeta)^2$	$+\epsilon^2$	$\vec{k}_1 \cdot \vec{k}_2$	G_{000}^1
B_3	$+2a\epsilon \dot{\zeta} (\nabla \zeta) (\nabla \chi)$	$+2\epsilon^2$	$\frac{\vec{k}_1 \cdot \vec{k}_2}{k_2^2}$	G_{011}^3
B_4	$-\frac{\epsilon}{2a} (\partial_i \zeta) (\partial^i \chi) \nabla^2 \chi$	$-\epsilon^3/2$	$\frac{\vec{k}_1 \cdot \vec{k}_2}{k_2^2}$	G_{011}^3
B_5	$-\frac{\epsilon}{4a} \nabla^2 \zeta (\nabla \chi)^2$	$-\epsilon^3/4$	$k_1^2 \frac{k_2 \cdot k_3}{k_2^2 k_3^2}$	G_{011}^3

TABLE II. Coefficients of the comoving perturbation during slow-roll inflation after pre-inflation vacuum influence.

Initial Condition	C_k	D_k
BD ^a	$\sqrt{\frac{1}{8k}} e^{-ik\eta_t} \left(\left(\frac{1}{k\eta_t} \right)^2 + 2i \left(\frac{1}{k\eta_t} \right) - 2 \right)$	$\sqrt{\frac{1}{8k}} e^{+ik\eta_t} \left(\frac{1}{k\eta_t} \right)^2$
HD ^{b,c}	$\sqrt{\frac{1}{8w_k}} e^{-ik\eta_t} \left(\left(\frac{1}{k\eta_t} \right)^2 + i \left(1 + \frac{w_k}{k} \right) \frac{1}{k\eta_t} - \left(1 + \frac{w_k}{k} \right) \right)$	$\sqrt{\frac{1}{8w_k}} e^{+ik\eta_t} \left(\left(\frac{1}{k\eta_t} \right)^2 - i \left(1 - \frac{w_k}{k} \right) \frac{1}{k\eta_t} - \left(1 - \frac{w_k}{k} \right) \right)$
RHM ^d	$\sqrt{\frac{\pi\eta_t}{32}} e^{-ik\eta_t} \left(H_0^{(2)} \left[\frac{k\eta_t}{2} \right] - \left(\frac{1}{k\eta_t} + i \right) H_1^{(2)} \left[\frac{k\eta_t}{2} \right] \right)$	$\sqrt{\frac{\pi\eta_t}{32}} e^{+ik\eta_t} \left(H_0^{(2)} \left[\frac{k\eta_t}{2} \right] - \left(\frac{1}{k\eta_t} - i \right) H_1^{(2)} \left[\frac{k\eta_t}{2} \right] \right)$
RSET ^e	$\sqrt{\frac{1}{8k}} e^{-ik\eta_t} \left(i \left(\frac{1}{k\eta_t} \right) - 2 \right)$	$\sqrt{\frac{1}{8k}} e^{+ik\eta_t} \left(i \left(\frac{1}{k\eta_t} \right) \right)$
FIC ^f	$\sqrt{\frac{3}{2}} R^{(0)} e^{-ik\eta_t} \left(J_0 \left[\frac{k\eta_t}{2} \right] - \left(\frac{1}{k\eta_t} + i \right) J_1 \left[\frac{k\eta_t}{2} \right] \right)$	$\sqrt{\frac{3}{2}} R^{(0)} e^{+ik\eta_t} \left(J_0 \left[\frac{k\eta_t}{2} \right] - \left(\frac{1}{k\eta_t} - i \right) J_1 \left[\frac{k\eta_t}{2} \right] \right)$

^a Bunch-Davies^b Hamiltonian Diagonalisation^c $w_k^2 = k^2 + \eta_t^{-2}$ ^d Right Handed Mode^e Renormalized Stressed Energy Tensor^f Frozen Initial Conditions, the only classical initial condition, imposed at the singularity.

whole \mathcal{S}_I function where the diverging term (*Real*{ I } ones) cancel each other (same as classical calculus [22]). It is visible when developing \mathcal{S}_I into W , X , Y , and Z which are defined and computed in Tab. IV.

Except when divergent integrals had to be manually calculated, results have been checked using *Mathematica* [29]. The calculations are trustworthy as the divergences perfectly matched with a cancelling counterpart but also, as explained later in section IV B, the usual slow-roll inflation results (see Appendix C) are recovered when η_{tr} is taken to usual ∞^+ .

$B_{1,3,4,5}$ can now be computed by permuting k_1 , k_2 and k_3 in G_{011}^3 and multiplying by the correct constants introduced in section III A.

At this stage, two different orders of slow-roll magnitudes are possible in the five contributions, which is comparable with classical inflation (see Appendix C): $f_{NL}^1, f_{NL}^2, f_{NL}^3 \propto \epsilon$ and $f_{NL}^4, f_{NL}^5 \propto \epsilon^2$. In this case (small ϵ), it means that contributions 4 and 5 will be negligible, which is consistent with previous studies [22] about the suppression of the non-Gaussianity by the slow-roll for a simple cosmological fluid.

C. Patterns and Asymptotes study

The present work takes advantage of a fast *python/numpy* code to compute the explicit bispectrums. The *plotly* package [30] has been used to deal with 3D

surface plots (e.g. Figure 4). As many divergences are encountered in this study, despite manual cutoffs, numerical artifacts can still be observed. The cubic meshes of the plots have at least 250³ points.

1. Shapes and variations

This section comments on Figure 4, which shows the resulting total shape function for the BD IC at different scales (with $\eta_t^{-1} = 1$ for the sake of simplicity). For smaller k , the plots require more points and scaling but have a similar appearance.

One will quickly recognize the local shape on each of these plots. This apparent shape is the same for any k . The sign of each turns out to be not necessarily the same as SR inflation (see Figure 6) and to be oscillating. This could be a direct consequence of the two-waves model (see Tab. IV) allowing interference and thus sign changes.

The differences between the IC choices themselves (BD, HD, RHM, RSET) are visible but not prominent which is why we chose to focus on the BD IC. It emphasizes the observation that all these vacua look similar but are different stages of a general form of shape evolving with the scale k . This remark is of course motivated by the great similarity between the initial conditions for the observed primordial spectrum and the small delay and difference which separate them in Fig. 2.

However, when looking at higher or smaller scales, the

FIG. 4. Total shape function at different values of k (in units of H_t) for the Bunch-Davies IC. The color scale is normalized between the different plots and uses a cutoff of the squeezed triangles divergences associated with $|S| \geq 2000$. $\eta_t^{-1} = 1$ for simplicity.

local shape keeps oscillating and shows a variation in its average plateau height. For instance, an equilateral shape appears with high scales. This reveals the necessity to give more credit to non-squeezed shapes and the explicit use of f_{NL} .

2. Asymptotic non-Gaussianities

In this section, we focus on the specific case of equilateral triangles ($k_1 = k_2 = k_3$) and study both the shape function $S(k) = k^6 B(k, k, k)$ and the reduced bispectrum $f_{\text{NL}}(k)$. From now on, we set arbitrarily the value $\eta_t = 1 \times 10^3$, so that we limit our study to $k \geq 100/\eta_t$ to simulate the constraint on the superiority of the CMB scale to the transition one (see Fig. 1). It must also be noticed that the present work uses rigorous o-notations for asymptotic calculus [31].

To describe the oscillations of the shape function and thus of the non-Gaussianities, the limits of the infinitely small wavelengths ($k \rightarrow +\infty$, 'UV' limit) and the infinite wavelengths ($k \rightarrow 0$, 'IR' limit) have been studied. This choice was made because the classical SR inflation shape and reduced bispectrum have finite bounds at these two limits. However, a few of our tests suggested it was not the case for the KD-sourced inflation.

The mathematical equivalents of all the auxiliary functions in Tab. II have been studied and expressed according to k and C_k , assuming asymptotic dominance or at least similarity of the latter against D_k . Appendix D explains the associated details, the results of which are summarized in Tab. III. The second contribution had to be treated separately since the auxiliary functions are different from the ones giving $B_{1,3,4,5}$.

Thus, substituting in these formulae the asymptotic equivalents of the IC coefficients by their possible values given in Tab. VI, one finds out that most contributions have a divergent shape and reduced bispectrum at both 0 and $+\infty$. The results are reported in Tab.V. The rare exceptions are the $k^6 B_{1,3,4,5}$, whatever the IC is, (phase

difference between C_k and D_k at 0 as explained in Appendix D).

Fig. 5 provides a plot of the non-Gaussian amplitudes for the equilateral triangles. It confirms that the current model suffers from IR-UV divergences with fast oscillations (due to the choice of η_t).

The conclusion behind these results, especially looking at Fig. 5, is surprising: all amplitudes of non-Gaussianities are allowed and grow with the experimental cutoff. While the classic SR f_{NL} barely reaches 0.01 for the same k cutoff as Fig. 5, here we have the possibility of oscillating scale-variant non-Gaussianities with an amplitude bigger than unity.

TABLE III. Asymptotic equivalents^a for the observables at infinitely small and great wavelengths. Details of the calculations are provided in the appendix.

Observable	0	$+\infty$ ^b
$k^6 B_{1,3,4,5}(k)$	$k^3 C_k ^6$ ^c	$k^4 C_k ^6$
$k^6 B_2(k)$	$k^4 C_k ^6$	$k^4 C_k ^6$
$f_{\text{NL}}^{1,3,4,5}(k)$	$k C_k ^2$	$k^4 C_k ^6$
$f_{\text{NL}}^2(k)$	$k^2 C_k ^2$	$k^4 C_k ^6$

^a Constants and oscillations have been set to 1 for simplicity.

^b These results assume that C_k dominates D_k at $+\infty$

^c As explained in the appendix, the phase difference between coefficients ($C_k =_0 e^{-2ik\eta_t} D_k$) at 0 can be exploited to have a vanishing (telescoping) limit.

IV. DIVERGENCES ANALYSIS

A. Choosing an initial state against divergence

In this section, we try to justify that there is no reason to believe that there exists an initial state at the transition that gives finite non-Gaussianities within our KD-sourced model, i.e. UV-IR convergent. For equilateral contributions and following Table III, we would need

FIG. 5. Analytical equilateral total reduced bispectrums, assuming usual quantum initial conditions for the spectrum. UV-IR divergences are cut above 1.5 magnitudes. The lines' width is due to fast oscillations ($\eta_t = 1 \times 10^3$). SR curve is the usual weak slow-roll reduced bispectrum. The IR limit is also an oscillating divergence.

the following conditions

$$\begin{aligned}
 (C_a) : & |C_k - D_k|^2 = \frac{1}{2k} + o_\infty(k^{-1}) = o_0(k^{-1}) \\
 (C_b) : & |C_k| = O_\infty(k^{-2/3}) \text{ and } |D_k| = O_\infty(k^{-2/3}) \\
 (C_c) : & |C_k| = O_0(k^{-1/2}) \text{ and } |D_k| = O_0(k^{-1/2}),
 \end{aligned} \tag{26}$$

where C_a ensures that the primordial spectrum (Fig. 2) remains convergent on both limits as usual and where C_b (resp. C_c) ensures that the reduced bispectrum (ie the non-Gaussianity) has finite bounds at $+\infty$ (resp 0).

1. Ultra-violet case

If, as the ones studied, we choose IC such that (C^∞ : $\frac{D_k}{C_k} = o_\infty(1)$) is verified, there is no way to verify C_a , C_b and C_c at the same time. In fact by the absurd, if C_a is verified, then C_b will not be since then C_a becomes $|C_k| \sim_\infty \frac{1}{\sqrt{2k}}$ which is incompatible with C_b . On the other hand, if C_b and C_c are verified then C_a will not be verified unless we accept a zero value for Δ at $+\infty$.

If C^∞ is not assumed, the result still holds. For this purpose, $|C_k - D_k|^2$ is developed as

$$|C_k - D_k|^2 =_\infty |C_k|^2 + |D_k|^2 - 2|C_k||D_k|\cos(\Delta_\infty\phi_k), \tag{27}$$

where $\Delta_\infty\phi_k$ is the phase difference at ∞ . We now apply C_a and C_b on both sides to get the following asymptotic equation

$$\frac{1}{2k} + o_\infty(k^{-1}) = O_\infty(k^{-4/3}), \tag{28}$$

as the sum in previous equation 27 is a sum of $O_\infty(k^{-4/3})$. But then multiplying this equation by $k^{4/3}$,

we quickly understand that it is impossible to choose values for C_k , D_k , and $\Delta_\infty\phi_k$ which solve this equation.

We just showed that the IC choice cannot cure the UV divergence without giving a false spectrum.

2. Infra-red case

For infinitely small scales, the conclusion is different. Using the same reasoning gives at $o_0(k^{-1})$ order

$$0 = k^{-1}[|f_{C,0}(k)|^2 + |f_{D,0}(k)|^2 - 2|f_{C,0}(k)||f_{D,0}(k)|\cos(\Delta_0\phi_k)], \tag{29}$$

where f functions are bounded such that $|C_k| =_0 k^{-\frac{1}{2}}|f_{C,0}(k)|$ and $|D_k| =_0 k^{-\frac{1}{2}}|f_{D,0}(k)|$. Here the simple example where these functions are taken as constants is feasible if we set the phase difference as $\Delta_0\phi_k = \lambda k^p$ and expand the cos function. As showed on Tab. VI, $\lambda = 0$ corresponds to the case of the Frozen Initial Condition [14] which is a classical condition and not a quantum one.

However, it is not a coincidence that the classical coefficients are the only ones to provide IR convergence because the normalization is different from the quantum ones. Indeed, C_k and D_k coefficients constitute the weights of a Bogolyubov transformation of the De Sitter IC [27] and must keep intact the canonical quantization of the Mukhanov-Sasaki solutions. This adds the condition (C_0) : $|C_k|^2 - |D_k|^2 = \frac{1}{2k}$ whereas this difference is 0 for a classical solution like FIC's [14].

To prove that (C_0) is strong enough to forbid IR-convergence for any quantum IC choice, it takes to assume that (*) : $\Delta_0\phi_k = o_0(1)$, so that eq. 29 entails $|f_{C,0}(k)| = |f_{D,0}(k)|$. In this case, (C_d) : $(|C_k| - |D_k|)(|C_k| + |D_k|) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2k}}$ is not respected at this order, which is absurd, whereas the classical (C_0) would be respected.

Under assumption (*), we showed that no quantum IC choice can cure the IR divergence without breaking the quantification. Giving up on the former (*), would demand a phase difference between the waves at the IR limit. That unusual case has not been treated here and is considered nonphysical.

B. Old transition framework

In this section, we explore a way to deal with UV-IR divergences by first identifying their source.

A simple situation can help to identify both problems. By assuming $D_k = 0$, it is then more convenient to write in the equilateral case

$$\begin{cases}
 f_{NL}^1(k) = -\frac{5}{3}\epsilon k|C_k|^2[-\frac{4}{9} + \frac{4}{9}\cos 3k\eta_t + \frac{k\eta_t}{3}\sin 3k\eta_t] \\
 f_{NL}^2(k) = -\frac{5}{6}\epsilon k|C_k|^2[-\frac{17}{9} + (\frac{1}{k\eta_t} - 3k\eta_t)\sin 3k\eta_t - \frac{10}{9}\cos 3k\eta_t],
 \end{cases} \tag{30}$$

The asymptotic UV-divergence is explicit for the different vacua as we can now see that

$$\begin{cases} f_{NL}^1(k) \sim_{\infty} -\frac{5}{9}\epsilon k^2 |C_k|^2 \sin 3k\eta_t \\ f_{NL}^2(k) \sim_{\infty} \frac{5}{2}\epsilon k^2 |C_k|^2 \sin 3k\eta_t, \end{cases} \quad (31)$$

which reconnects with our UV results in Table III and Figure 5. However, convergence is obtained at 0 as we removed reflected waves ($D_k = 0$) that cause interfering terms and make it more difficult to converge. We just identified the origin of IR divergences.

From here, it is interesting to notice that oscillating diverging functions in eq. 30 and 31 come from the finite interval of the in-in integration (see eq. 20) rather than the complex semi-infinite one (to $-\infty^{\pm}$). This is perfectly illustrated by the example: $\int_{-\infty^+}^0 x e^{ikx} dx = k^{-2}$ whereas $\int_{x_0}^0 e^{ikx} dx = [1 + e^{ikx_0}(ikx_0 - 1)]k^{-2}$. The order in powers of k is changed because there is no destruction of the phases in the integration. So we can say that the divergences are brought when there is a conformal-finite wave phase difference between the vacuum influence and the end of inflation. [32] This raised divergence echoes the Hamiltonian Diagonalization's one, where the IC is imposed on the Hamiltonian at a finite conformal time [12]. This method has been criticized [33] because of the infinite densities that it brings when thinking about particle creation and annihilation before and after the IC point that is not at $-\infty^{\pm}$. It also means that the solutions can probably be the same: if those divergences are wrong, there could be some sort of renormalisation method from the start.

Many Inflationary models provide divergences. In-In literature is usually dismissive regarding the worries about divergences. Indeed, the only worries one should have is the domain of validity and the cutoff.

C. Validity of the model: what's next?

In this paper, we extended techniques from the 2-point spectrum to In-In formalism and justified the use of IC in a finite past because of our KD-SR model. However, integrating In-In integrals from a state in a finite past only suggests that we can neglect any interactions before that time. This way, one is building an EFT of Inflation [34], where the cutoff (time) needs to be deep enough in the CMB scale horizon (see Figure 1). If one does not include any other contributions for correlators then after the transition time, the validity of this model constrains this time to be such that $k \gg \eta_t^{-1}$ for any scale of interest k . This is an 'old' transition framework.

What happens when η_t goes to $+\infty$? One should recover the usual In-In result with a BD vacuum [22]: the Hubble radius at the transition approaches 0, i.e. the IC is being imposed as usual. This only works when imposing the usual BD values for the IC. Indeed, the usual $\eta_t = -\infty^+$ limit trick in the complex plane only makes

$-ik\eta_t$ waves vanish and without a wise choice for D_k , none of the multiple overall $+ik\eta_t$ waves in Table IV will stay under control. The real problem with this is that physics put bounds on the value of D_k coefficients [34] and this has been overlooked so far in the KDSR literature. Since our initial state is equivalent to an excited state built upon the BD vacuum, the associated 'particles' might dominate the background through backreaction and hamper successful inflation. In [34, 35], it is shown that the choice of D_k determines the energy density of those particles. The authors thus propose sufficient UV falloffs of the D_k coefficients ($D_k \simeq e^{-k\eta_t}$ or $\leq \frac{1}{k^5}$) to keep the energy density under control against backreaction effects. Any further works on KD-SR correlators should now include this criterion which means reviewing the usual coefficients used for the transition state.

Finally, the present work is neglecting the Kinetic era contribution to the bispectrum. By following past assumptions [26, 36] that a Kinetic era plays a homogenizing role and makes difficult the definition of the interacting vacuum, it is although wrong to assume that no imprint could be left on perturbations. This is even more striking when remembering that the Hubble radius is increasing during this type of pre-inflation and fully allows interactions. Bringing back this calculation on the table could also extend the domain of validity of our model and undo the necessity of the old transition framework. This last paragraph is thus a call for additional work on the matter.

V. CONCLUSION

As a continuation of ongoing efforts to connect inflation theory with primordial observables, this study had the purpose to extend previous works on the primordial spectrum powered by a kinetic pre-inflation and slow-roll inflation [14] to the case of the bispectrum.

The five main contributions to the bispectrum have been derived for the truncated slow-roll inflation model influenced by a vacuum at its maximum influence in a finite conformal past. As a single-field and elementary model, this kind of inflation is the simplest of its genre. While using a constant slow-roll approximation does not produce enough non-Gaussianities to fit modern data, this approach was primarily aimed at studying the changes brought to the usual scenario by the introduction of a pre-inflationary kinetic era with a singularity.

This study highlighted an interesting invariance-breaking bispectrum induced from a necessary -but no less interesting- adaptation of the In-In formalism. Indeed, the imposition of a vacuum in a finite past required the modification of a well-established derivation, which was not without questionable consequences. Without any correction, the bispectrum appears with oscillating shapes (mainly local patterns) that diverge for UV and IR scales using all usual quantum ICs of the scalar power

spectrum.

The source of the new divergences compared to the vanilla case has been searched for. The study lead to the conclusion that no choice of IC could cure the UV divergence, but rather that the diverging magnitudes were coming from the truncation of the In-In integral at a finite time. Those divergences are thus part of the truncation models, with any choice of wave coefficients, not just KDSR ones.

Finally, we chose to question the domain of validity of our model as it neglects what happens before the transition time regarding interactions. We found out that the literature provides answers if the transition is assumed to be the starting point of interactions: it is about building an EFT of Inflation. This requires careful handling of the reflective coefficients in the construction of the transition state: it controls the energy density of the particles built upon the BD vacuum and needs to remain under control against the background to avoid any failure in inflating. However, this only happens to be needed if the past of the transition is without interactions. But it is unlikely to be the case as kinetic pre-inflation sees an increasing Hubble radius and so potential interactions of certain scales before inflation. Therefore, we emphasize here the need for further work on the proper use of In In formalism for the full KDSR contribution. An eventual solution could be the use of a numerical evaluation [37].

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Appendix A: Details of the In-In formalism

The method to compute this quantity is inspired by the Quantum Field Theory as follows:

- Fourier transform of perturbations and their derivatives write as:

$$\zeta(\vec{x}, t) = \int \frac{d^3 p}{(2\pi)^3} \zeta_p(t) e^{i\vec{p}\cdot\vec{x}}$$

$$\dot{\zeta}(\vec{x}, t) = \int \frac{d^3 p}{(2\pi)^3} \dot{\zeta}_p(t) e^{i\vec{p}\cdot\vec{x}}$$

$$\zeta(\vec{x}, t) = \int \frac{d^3 p}{(2\pi)^3} \zeta_p(t) e^{i\vec{p}\cdot\vec{x}}$$

$$\nabla\zeta(\vec{x}, t) = \int \frac{d^3 p}{(2\pi)^3} i\vec{p}\zeta_p(t) e^{i\vec{p}\cdot\vec{x}}$$

$$\nabla\chi(\vec{x}, t) = -i\epsilon a^4 \int \frac{d^3 p}{(2\pi)^3} \frac{\vec{p}}{p^2} \dot{\zeta}_p(t) e^{i\vec{p}\cdot\vec{x}}$$

- We can now transform $H(t) = \lambda a^q(t) \times \int d^3 x \int \frac{d^3 p_1 d^3 p_2 d^3 p_3}{(2\pi)^9} f(\vec{p}_1, \vec{p}_2, \vec{p}_3) \frac{d^l \zeta_{p_1}}{dt^l} \frac{d^m \zeta_{p_2}}{dt^m} \frac{d^n \zeta_{p_3}}{dt^n} e^{i(\vec{p}_1 + \vec{p}_2 + \vec{p}_3)\cdot\vec{x}}$ after injection Fourier transform with q a non-negative integer and l, m, n equal to 0 or 1.
- Quantification of the perturbation with the relation: $\hat{\zeta}_k = \hat{\zeta}_k^+ + \hat{\zeta}_k^- = u_k \hat{a}_k + u_k^* \hat{a}_k^\dagger$ where \hat{a}_k and \hat{a}_k^\dagger are the annihilation and creation operators associated to the background quantum problem: $[\hat{a}_{k_1}, \hat{a}_{k_2}^\dagger] = (2\pi)^3 \delta^{(3)}(\vec{k}_1 + \vec{k}_2)$. The only non-zero commutation relation for ζ is then: $[\zeta_{k_1}^+(t_1), \zeta_{k_2}^-(t_2)] = (2\pi)^3 u_{k_1}(t_1) u_{k_2}^*(t_2) \delta^{(3)}(\vec{k}_1 + \vec{k}_2)$.
- $\langle \zeta_{k_1}(\eta_t) \zeta_{k_2}(\eta_t) \zeta_{k_3}(\eta_t) \rangle$ is given by Wick's theorem in the interaction picture at first order for the evolution operator (given by H) and keeping only non-zero terms of the form: $[\zeta_{k_1}^+(t_1), \zeta_{p_1}^-(t)] [\zeta_{k_2}^+(t_1), \zeta_{p_2}^-(t)] [\zeta_{k_3}^+(t_1), \zeta_{p_3}^-(t)]$. Permutations of indices appear in the multiple contractions and must be made explicit.

Appendix B: Permutations in the contributions

1. Contribution 1: $\zeta\zeta^2$

$$\begin{aligned}
B_1(k_1, k_2, k_3) &= 2\lambda_1 f_1(\vec{k}_1, \vec{k}_2, \vec{k}_3) \text{Im} [u_{k_1}(\eta_t) u_{k_2}(\eta_t) u_{k_3}(\eta_t) G_{011}^3(k_1, k_2, k_3, \eta_t)] + \text{permutations} \\
&= -2\epsilon^2 \times 2 \text{Im} [u_{k_1}(\eta_t) u_{k_2}(\eta_t) u_{k_3}(\eta_t) (G_{011}^3(k_1, k_2, k_3, \eta_t) + G_{110}^3(k_1, k_2, k_3, \eta_t) + G_{101}^3(k_1, k_2, k_3, \eta_t))] \\
&= -4\epsilon^2 \text{Im} [u_{k_1}(\eta_t) u_{k_2}(\eta_t) u_{k_3}(\eta_t) (G_{011}^3(k_1, k_2, k_3, \eta_t) + G_{110}^3(k_1, k_2, k_3, \eta_t) + G_{101}^3(k_1, k_2, k_3, \eta_t))] \\
&\quad (\text{B1})
\end{aligned}$$

2. Contribution 2: $\zeta(\nabla\zeta)^2$

$$\begin{aligned}
B_2(k_1, k_2, k_3) &= 2\lambda_2 f_2(\vec{k}_1, \vec{k}_2, \vec{k}_3) \text{Im} [u_{k_1}(\eta_t) u_{k_2}(\eta_t) u_{k_3}(\eta_t) G_{000}^1(k_1, k_2, k_3, \eta_t)] + \text{permutations} \\
&= 2\epsilon^2 \times 2(\vec{k}_1 \cdot \vec{k}_2 + \vec{k}_1 \cdot \vec{k}_3 + \vec{k}_2 \cdot \vec{k}_3) \text{Im} [u_{k_1}(\eta_t) u_{k_2}(\eta_t) u_{k_3}(\eta_t) G_{000}^1(k_1, k_2, k_3, \eta_t)] \\
&= 2\epsilon^2(k_1^2 + k_2^2 + k_3^2) \text{Im} [u_{k_1}(\eta_t) u_{k_2}(\eta_t) u_{k_3}(\eta_t) G_{000}^1(k_1, k_2, k_3, \eta_t)] \\
&\quad (\text{B2})
\end{aligned}$$

3. Contribution 3: $\dot{\zeta}(\nabla\zeta)(\nabla\chi)$

$$\begin{aligned}
B_3(k_1, k_2, k_3) &= 2\lambda_3 f_3(\vec{k}_1, \vec{k}_2, \vec{k}_3) \text{Im} [u_{k_1}(\eta_t) u_{k_2}(\eta_t) u_{k_3}(\eta_t) G_{101}^3(k_1, k_2, k_3, \eta_t)] + \text{permutations} \\
&= 4\epsilon^2 \text{Im} \left[u_{k_1}(\eta_t) u_{k_2}(\eta_t) u_{k_3}(\eta_t) \left(\left(\frac{\vec{k}_2 \cdot \vec{k}_3}{k_3^2} + \frac{\vec{k}_2 \cdot \vec{k}_1}{k_1^2} \right) G_{101}^3(k_1, k_2, k_3, \eta_t) \right. \right. \\
&\quad \left. \left. + \left(\frac{\vec{k}_3 \cdot \vec{k}_1}{k_1^2} + \frac{\vec{k}_3 \cdot \vec{k}_2}{k_2^2} \right) G_{110}^3(k_1, k_2, k_3, \eta_t) + \left(\frac{\vec{k}_1 \cdot \vec{k}_2}{k_2^2} + \frac{\vec{k}_1 \cdot \vec{k}_3}{k_3^2} \right) G_{011}^3(k_1, k_2, k_3, \eta_t) \right) \right] \\
&= 4\epsilon^2 \text{Im} \left[u_{k_1}(\eta_t) u_{k_2}(\eta_t) u_{k_3}(\eta_t) \left(\left(1 + \frac{k_2^2 - k_3^2}{k_1^2} + \frac{k_2^2 - k_1^2}{k_3^2} \right) G_{101}^3(k_1, k_2, k_3, \eta_t) \right. \right. \\
&\quad \left. \left. + \left(1 + \frac{k_3^2 - k_2^2}{k_1^2} + \frac{k_3^2 - k_1^2}{k_2^2} \right) G_{110}^3(k_1, k_2, k_3, \eta_t) + \left(1 + \frac{k_1^2 - k_2^2}{k_3^2} + \frac{k_1^2 - k_3^2}{k_2^2} \right) G_{011}^3(k_1, k_2, k_3, \eta_t) \right) \right] \\
&\quad (\text{B3})
\end{aligned}$$

4. Contribution 4: $(\nabla\zeta)(\nabla\chi)\nabla^2\chi$

$$\begin{aligned}
B_4(k_1, k_2, k_3) &= 2\lambda_4 f_4(\vec{k}_1, \vec{k}_2, \vec{k}_3) \text{Im} [u_{k_1}(\eta_t) u_{k_2}(\eta_t) u_{k_3}(\eta_t) G_{101}^3(k_1, k_2, k_3, \eta_t)] + \text{permutations} \\
&= -\frac{\epsilon}{4} B_3(k_1, k_2, k_3) \\
&= -\epsilon^3 \text{Im} \left[u_{k_1}(\eta_t) u_{k_2}(\eta_t) u_{k_3}(\eta_t) \left(\left(1 + \frac{k_2^2 - k_3^2}{k_1^2} + \frac{k_2^2 - k_1^2}{k_3^2} \right) G_{101}^3(k_1, k_2, k_3, \eta_t) \right. \right. \\
&\quad \left. \left. + \left(1 + \frac{k_3^2 - k_2^2}{k_1^2} + \frac{k_3^2 - k_1^2}{k_2^2} \right) G_{110}^3(k_1, k_2, k_3, \eta_t) + \left(1 + \frac{k_1^2 - k_2^2}{k_3^2} + \frac{k_1^2 - k_3^2}{k_2^2} \right) G_{011}^3(k_1, k_2, k_3, \eta_t) \right) \right] \\
&\quad (\text{B4})
\end{aligned}$$

5. Contribution 5: $\nabla^2\zeta(\nabla\chi)^2$

$$\begin{aligned}
B_5(k_1, k_2, k_3) &= 2\lambda_5 f_5(\vec{k}_1, \vec{k}_2, \vec{k}_3) \text{Im} [u_{k_1}(\eta_t) u_{k_2}(\eta_t) u_{k_3}(\eta_t) G_{101}^3(k_1, k_2, k_3, \eta_t)] + \text{permutations} \\
&= -\frac{\epsilon^3}{2} \times 2 \text{Im} [u_{k_1}(\eta_t) u_{k_2}(\eta_t) u_{k_3}(\eta_t) (k_1^2 \frac{\vec{k}_2 \cdot \vec{k}_3}{k_2^2 k_3^2} G_{011}^3(k_1, k_2, k_3, \eta_t) \\
&\quad + (k_2^2 \frac{\vec{k}_1 \cdot \vec{k}_3}{k_2^2 k_3^2} G_{101}^3(k_1, k_2, k_3, \eta_t) + (k_3^2 \frac{\vec{k}_1 \cdot \vec{k}_2}{k_1^2 k_2^2} G_{110}^3(k_1, k_2, k_3, \eta_t))] \\
&= -\frac{\epsilon^3}{2} \text{Im} [u_{k_1}(\eta_t) u_{k_2}(\eta_t) u_{k_3}(\eta_t) (k_1^4 (\frac{1}{k_1^2 k_2^2} + \frac{1}{k_2^2 k_3^2} - \frac{1}{k_2^2 k_3^2}) G_{011}^3(k_1, k_2, k_3, \eta_t) \\
&\quad + k_2^4 (\frac{1}{k_2^2 k_1^2} + \frac{1}{k_2^2 k_3^2} - \frac{1}{k_1^2 k_3^2}) G_{101}^3(k_1, k_2, k_3, \eta_t) + k_3^4 (\frac{1}{k_3^2 k_1^2} + \frac{1}{k_3^2 k_2^2} - \frac{1}{k_1^2 k_2^2}) G_{110}^3(k_1, k_2, k_3, \eta_t))] \\
&\quad (\text{B5})
\end{aligned}$$

TABLE IV. Auxiliary functions used to compute bispectrum integrals. These formulae are the most simplified known ones.

Function	Implicit and explicit values ^{a b c}
$S_R(k_1, k_2, k_3, \eta_t)$	$Im\{(C_{k_1} - D_{k_1})(C_{k_2} - D_{k_2})(C_{k_3} - D_{k_3}) \sum_{(P_{k_1}, P_{k_2}, P_{k_3}) \in \{C_k^*, -D_k^*\}^3} P_{k_1} P_{k_2} P_{k_3} R_{\alpha(P_{k_1})\alpha(P_{k_2})\alpha(P_{k_3})}(k_1, k_2, k_3, \eta_t)\}$
$S_F(k_1, k_2, k_3, \eta_t)$	$Im\{(C_{k_1} - D_{k_1})(C_{k_2} - D_{k_2})(C_{k_3} - D_{k_3}) \sum_{(P_{k_1}, P_{k_2}, P_{k_3}) \in \{C_k^*, -D_k^*\}^3} P_{k_1} P_{k_2} P_{k_3} F_{\alpha(P_{k_1})\alpha(P_{k_2})\alpha(P_{k_3})}(k_1, k_2, k_3, \eta_t)\}$
$S_I(k_1, k_2, k_3, \eta_t)$	$Im\{(C_{k_1} - D_{k_1})(C_{k_2} - D_{k_2})(C_{k_3} - D_{k_3}) \sum_{(P_{k_1}, P_{k_2}, P_{k_3}) \in \{C_k^*, -D_k^*\}^3} P_{k_1} P_{k_2} P_{k_3} I_{k_1\alpha(P_{k_1})+k_2\alpha(P_{k_2})+k_3\alpha(P_{k_3})}(\eta_t)\}$ $= W(k_1, k_2, k_3, \eta_t) + X(k_1, k_2, k_3, \eta_t) + X(k_1, k_3, k_2, \eta_t) + X(k_2, k_3, k_1, \eta_t)$ $+ Y(k_1, k_2, k_3, \eta_t) + Y(k_2, k_1, k_3, \eta_t) + Y(k_3, k_1, k_2, \eta_t) + Z(k_1, k_2, k_3, \eta_t)$
$R_{abc}(k_1, k_2, k_3, \eta_t)$	$\int_0^{\eta_t} (1 - ia k_1(\eta - \eta_t)) e^{i(ak_1 + bk_2 + ck_3)(\eta - \eta_t)} d\eta$ $= \begin{cases} \eta_t + \frac{i}{2} a k_1 \eta_t^2 & \text{if } ak_1 + bk_2 + ck_3 = 0 \\ \frac{e^{-i\eta_t(ak_1 + bk_2 + ck_3)} [(i - a\eta_t k_1)(ak_1 + bk_2 + ck_3) + ia k_1] - i(ak_1 + bk_2 + ck_3) - ia k_1}{(ak_1 + bk_2 + ck_3)^2} & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$
$F_{abc}(k_1, k_2, k_3, \eta_t)$	$\int_0^{\eta_t} (iabc k_1 k_2 k_3 (\eta - \eta_t) - abk_1 k_2 - ack_1 k_3 - bck_2 k_3) e^{i(ak_1 + bk_2 + ck_3)(\eta - \eta_t)} d\eta$ $= \begin{cases} -\eta_t (bck_2 k_3 + ack_1 k_3 + abk_1 k_2 + \frac{1}{2} iabc \eta_t k_1 k_2 k_3) & \text{if } ak_1 + bk_2 + ck_3 = 0 \\ \frac{e^{-i\eta_t(ak_1 + bk_2 + ck_3)}}{(ak_1 + bk_2 + ck_3)^2} (a^2 k_1^2 (i(bk_2 + ck_3) e^{i\eta_t(ak_1 + bk_2 + ck_3)} + bk_2 (c\eta_t k_3 - i) - ick_3) \\ + ak_1 (i(b^2 k_2^2 + 4bck_2 k_3 + c^2 k_3^2) e^{i\eta_t(ak_1 + bk_2 + ck_3)} + b^2 c\eta_t k_2^2 k_3 - ib^2 k_2^2 + bc^2 \eta_t k_2 k_3^2 \\ - 4ibck_2 k_3 - ic^2 k_3^2) + ibck_2 k_3 (bk_2 + ck_3) (e^{i\eta_t(ak_1 + bk_2 + ck_3)} - 1)) & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$
^d $Im\{I_s(\eta_t)\}$	$Im\left\{\int_0^{\eta_t} (1 - is(\eta - \eta_t)) \frac{e^{is(\eta - \eta_t)}}{(\eta - \eta_t)^2} d\eta\right\} = s(\text{sinc}(s\eta_t) - 1)$
$W(k_1, k_2, k_3, \eta_t)$	$\sum_{(P_{k_1}, P_{k_2}, P_{k_3}) \in \{C_k^*, -D_k^*\}^3} P_{k_1} ^2 P_{k_2} ^2 P_{k_3} ^2 Im\{I_{k_1\alpha(P_{k_1})+k_2\alpha(P_{k_2})+k_3\alpha(P_{k_3})}(\eta_t)\}$ $= \sum_{(P_{k_1}, P_{k_2}, P_{k_3}) \in \{C_k^*, -D_k^*\}^3} P_{k_1} ^2 P_{k_2} ^2 P_{k_3} ^2$ $\times \{[k_1\alpha(P_{k_1}) + k_2\alpha(P_{k_2}) + k_3\alpha(P_{k_3})] [\text{sinc}(k_1\alpha(P_{k_1})\eta_t + k_2\alpha(P_{k_2})\eta_t + k_3\alpha(P_{k_3})\eta_t) - 1]\}$
$X(k_1, k_2, k_3, \eta_t)$	$-\sum_{(P_{k_1}, P_{k_2}) \in \{C_k^*, -D_k^*\}^2} P_{k_1} ^2 P_{k_2} ^2$ $\times [Im\{C_{k_3} D_{k_3}^* I_{k_1\alpha(P_{k_1})+k_2\alpha(P_{k_2})-k_3}(\eta_t) + Im\{D_{k_3} C_{k_3}^* I_{k_1\alpha(P_{k_1})+k_2\alpha(P_{k_2})+k_3}(\eta_t)\}]$ $= -\sum_{(P_{k_1}, P_{k_2}) \in \{C_k^*, -D_k^*\}^2} P_{k_1} ^2 P_{k_2} ^2$ $\times [Re\{C_{k_3} D_{k_3}^*\} Im\{I_{k_1\alpha(P_{k_1})+k_2\alpha(P_{k_2})-k_3}(\eta_t) + I_{k_1\alpha(P_{k_1})+k_2\alpha(P_{k_2})+k_3}(\eta_t)\}]$ $+ Im\{C_{k_3} D_{k_3}^*\} \mathcal{L}(k_1\alpha(P_{k_1}) + k_2\alpha(P_{k_2}) - k_3, k_1\alpha(P_{k_1}) + k_2\alpha(P_{k_2}) + k_3, \eta_t)]$
$Y(k_1, k_2, k_3, \eta_t)$	$\sum_{(P_{k_1}) \in \{C_{k_1}^*, -D_{k_1}^*\}} P_{k_1} ^2$ $\times [Im\{C_{k_2} D_{k_2}^* C_{k_3} D_{k_3}^* I_{k_1\alpha(P_{k_1})-k_2-k_3}(\eta_t) + Im\{D_{k_2} C_{k_2}^* D_{k_3} C_{k_3}^* I_{k_1\alpha(P_{k_1})+k_2+k_3}(\eta_t)\}]$ $+ Im\{C_{k_2} D_{k_2}^* D_{k_3} C_{k_3}^* I_{k_1\alpha(P_{k_1})-k_2+k_3}(\eta_t) + Im\{D_{k_2} C_{k_2}^* C_{k_3} D_{k_3}^* I_{k_1\alpha(P_{k_1})+k_2-k_3}(\eta_t)\}]$ $= \sum_{(P_{k_1}) \in \{C_{k_1}^*, -D_{k_1}^*\}} P_{k_1} ^2$ $\times [Re\{C_{k_2} D_{k_2}^* C_{k_3} D_{k_3}^*\} Im\{I_{k_1\alpha(P_{k_1})-k_2-k_3}(\eta_t) + I_{k_1\alpha(P_{k_1})+k_2+k_3}(\eta_t)\}]$ $+ Re\{C_{k_2} D_{k_2}^* D_{k_3} C_{k_3}^*\} Im\{I_{k_1\alpha(P_{k_1})-k_2+k_3}(\eta_t) + I_{k_1\alpha(P_{k_1})+k_2-k_3}(\eta_t)\}]$ $+ Im\{C_{k_2} D_{k_2}^* C_{k_3} D_{k_3}^*\} \mathcal{L}(k_1\alpha(P_{k_1}) - k_2 - k_3, k_1\alpha(P_{k_1}) + k_2 + k_3, \eta_t)$ $+ Im\{C_{k_2} D_{k_2}^* D_{k_3} C_{k_3}^*\} \mathcal{L}(k_1\alpha(P_{k_1}) - k_2 + k_3, k_1\alpha(P_{k_1}) + k_2 - k_3, \eta_t)]$
^{e f} $Z(k_1, k_2, k_3, \eta_t)$	$-\sum_{(P_{k_1}, P_{k_2}, P_{k_3}) \in \{C_k, -D_k\}^3} Im\{P_{k_1} \bar{P}_{k_1}^* P_{k_2} \bar{P}_{k_2}^* P_{k_3} \bar{P}_{k_3}^* I_{k_1\alpha(\bar{P}_{k_1}^*)+k_2\alpha(\bar{P}_{k_2}^*)+k_3\alpha(\bar{P}_{k_3}^*)}(\eta_t)\}$ $= -\sum Im\{P_{k_1} \bar{P}_{k_1}^* P_{k_2} \bar{P}_{k_2}^* P_{k_3} \bar{P}_{k_3}^* I_{k_1\alpha(\bar{P}_{k_1}^*)+k_2\alpha(\bar{P}_{k_2}^*)+k_3\alpha(\bar{P}_{k_3}^*)}(\eta_t)$ $+ P_{k_1}^* \bar{P}_{k_1} P_{k_2}^* \bar{P}_{k_2} P_{k_3}^* \bar{P}_{k_3} I_{-k_1\alpha(\bar{P}_{k_1}^*)-k_2\alpha(\bar{P}_{k_2}^*)-k_3\alpha(\bar{P}_{k_3}^*)}(\eta_t)\}$ $= 0$
$\mathcal{L}(K_1, K_2)$	$Re[I_{K_1}(\eta_t)] - Re[I_{K_2}(\eta_t)] = \frac{2}{\eta_t} \sin(\frac{K_1+K_2}{2}\eta_t) \sin(\frac{K_1-K_2}{2}\eta_t) + 2K_1 Si(K_1\eta_t) - 2K_2 Si(K_2\eta_t)$

^a where $\alpha(C_k^*) = +1$ and $\alpha(-D_k^*) = -1$.^b where $\{C_k^*, -D_k^*\}^3 = \{C_{k_1}^*, -D_{k_1}^*\} \times \{C_{k_2}^*, -D_{k_2}^*\} \times \{C_{k_3}^*, -D_{k_3}^*\}$.^c Despite some cases disjunctions, all expression are continuous at the $ak_1 + bk_2 + ck_3 = 0$ points.^d where sinc is a cardinal sinus.^e Where $\bar{C}_k = D_k$ and $\bar{D}_k = C_k$.^f This calculus uses $I_s^* = I_{-s}$.

FIG. 6. **Re-do** Total shape function for classical inflation using triangular parametrization. $\epsilon = 0.01$.

Appendix C: Bispectrum of a slow-roll single-field inflation

It is equivalent to setting $C_k = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2k}}$, $D_k = 0$, $u = u^{SR}$ and $\eta_0 = -\infty(1+i\gamma) = -\infty^+$, with γ going towards zero after integration. As commonly denoted in literature, we set the running $K = k_1 + k_2 + k_3$. The calculus leads to the following contributions

$$\begin{cases} B_1(k_1, k_2, k_3) = \frac{H_t^4}{16\epsilon} \frac{1}{k_1^3 k_2^3 k_3^3} \left(\frac{k_2^2 k_3^2}{K} + \frac{k_1 k_2^2 k_3^2}{K^2} \right) + 2sym. \\ B_2(k_1, k_2, k_3) = \frac{H_t^4}{16\epsilon} \frac{1}{k_1^3 k_2^3 k_3^3} (k_1 \cdot k_2) \\ \quad \times (-K + \frac{k_1 k_2 + k_2 k_3 + k_1 k_3}{K} + \frac{k_1 k_2 k_3}{K^2}) + 2sym. \\ B_3(k_1, k_2, k_3) = -\frac{H_t^4}{16\epsilon} \frac{1}{k_1^3 k_2^3 k_3^3} \frac{(k_1 \cdot k_2) k_3^2}{K} (2 + \frac{k_1 + k_2}{K}) + 2sym. \\ B_4(k_1, k_2, k_3) = \frac{H_t^4}{64} \frac{1}{k_1^3 k_2^3 k_3^3} \frac{(k_1 \cdot k_2) k_3^2}{K} (2 + \frac{k_1 + k_2}{K}) + 2sym. \\ B_5(k_1, k_2, k_3) = \frac{H_t^4}{64} \frac{1}{k_1^3 k_2^3 k_3^3} \frac{(k_1 \cdot k_2) k_3^2}{K} (1 + \frac{k_3}{K}) + 2sym., \end{cases} \quad (C1)$$

Where each contribution is a sum of 3 permutations of the indices and keeping implicit the delta functions. The result is consistent with literature [22]. The total shape function is plotted on Fig. 6 and refers to the well-known 'local shape': divergent -and so dominating- squeezed triangles contributions (corresponding to the corners of the figure, i.e. triangles where one of the k_i sides tends towards 0).

Appendix D: Asymptotic calculus

1. Infinitely small wavelengths

This corresponds to the case $k \rightarrow +\infty$.

Looking at usual C_k , D_k (see table II) encoding the initial conditions of inflation, one finds out that the (C_k) are dominating the (D_k) (let's call it condition (C^∞)), the latter corresponding to $+ik\eta$ waves. In this context, an equivalent expression at $+\infty$ for G and then $B(k)$ would be made of C_k terms only.

For this study, we need the following three equivalents at infinite k

$$\begin{cases} R_3(k) &= -\frac{4i}{9k} - \frac{\eta_t}{3} e^{-3ik\eta_t} + o_\infty(k^{-1}) \\ &= \frac{\eta_t}{3} e^{-3ik\eta_t} + o_\infty(1) \\ Im[F_{111}(\eta_t)] &= -\frac{\eta_t}{3} k^2 \sin 3k\eta_t + o_\infty(k^2) \\ Im[I_{3k}] &= -3k + o_\infty(k) = o_\infty(k^2), \end{cases} \quad (D1)$$

A comment can be made here: the exponential terms are direct consequences of the finite integrals. Indeed, replacing η_t (being the boundary) by ∞^+ would drop a power of k and would give convergent expressions with $C_k = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2k}}$ and $D_k = 0$. Assuming $\eta_t \gg 1$ would bring back the convergence of all observables but would then give classical inflation results and the KD era would be erased. However, let us pretend it is not the case here. By keeping the greatest orders (order 0 for R and 2 for F and I), we have the following consequences

$$\begin{cases} G_{011}^3 &\propto_\infty k (C_k^*)^3 Im[R_3(k)] \\ &\propto_\infty k (C_k^*)^3 \sin(3k\eta_t) \\ G_{000}^1 &\propto_\infty \frac{(C_k^*)^3}{k^3} Im[F_{111}(k)] \\ &\propto_\infty \frac{(C_k^*)^3}{k} \sin(3k\eta_t), \end{cases} \quad (D2)$$

Which implies that

$$\begin{cases} k^6 B_{1,3,4,5}(k) &\propto k^6 Im[u_k(\eta_t)^3 G_{011}^3] \\ &\propto_\infty k^6 \frac{|C_k|^6}{k^3} \propto_\infty k^4 |C_k|^6 \\ k^6 B_2(k) &\propto k^6 k^2 Im[u_k(\eta_t)^3 G_{000}^1] \\ &\propto_\infty k^6 k^2 \frac{|C_k|^6}{k^4} \propto_\infty k^4 |C_k|^6, \end{cases} \quad (D3)$$

2. Infinite wavelengths

This corresponds to the case $k \rightarrow 0$.

This time, $\{C_k\}$ and $\{D_k\}$ are of the same magnitude but with a different phase. This allows us to restrict ourselves to the study of the C_k^3 term only, again. Using

$$\begin{cases} R_3(k) &= -\frac{4i}{9k} + o_0(k^{-1}) \\ Im[F_{111}(\eta_t)] &= -3\eta_t k^2 + o_0(k^2) \\ Im[I_{3k}] &= -\frac{9}{2}\eta_t^2 k^3 + o_0(k^3) = o_0(k^2), \end{cases} \quad (D4)$$

It follows then

$$\begin{cases} k^6 B_{1,3,4,5}(k) &\propto_0 k^6 Im[u_k(\eta_t)^3 G_{011}^3] \\ &\propto_0 k^6 \frac{|C_k|^6}{k^3} \propto_0 k^3 |C_k|^6 \\ k^6 B_2(k) &\propto_0 k^6 k^2 Im[u_k(\eta_t)^3 G_{000}^1] \\ &\propto_0 k^6 k^2 \frac{|C_k|^6}{k^4} \propto_0 k^4 |C_k|^6 \\ f_{NL}^{1,3,4,5}(k) &\propto_0 \frac{k^3 |C_k|^4}{k^2 |C_k|^4} \propto_0 k |C_k|^2 \\ f_{NL}^2(k) &\propto_0 \frac{k^4 |C_k|^6}{k^2 |C_k|^4} \propto_0 k^2 |C_k|^2, \end{cases} \quad (D5)$$

Looking at the numerical results (see fig 3 and 4) suggests that the phase difference between coefficients ($C_k = 0$ $e^{-2ik\eta_t} D_k$) at 0 could be exploited to have a vanishing (telescoping) limit: using $C_k = 0$ $e^{-2ik\eta_t} D_k$ and $F_{abc}(k) \propto_0 e^{-ik(a+b+c)\eta_t}$ in $B_{1,3,4,5}$ and factorizing k and C_k factors gives 0.

TABLE V. Convergence (CV) or divergence (DV) of the different observables for the studied vacua. Full agreement between theory (see Tab. III and numerical plots (see Fig. 5).

Initial Cond.	Observables equi.	0	∞
BD	$k^6 B_{1,3,4,5}(k)$	CV	DV
	$k^6 B_2(k)$	DV	DV
	$f_{\text{NL}}^{1,3,4,5}(k)$	DV	DV
	$f_{\text{NL}}^2(k)$	DV	DV
HD	$k^6 B_{1,3,4,5}(k)$	CV	DV
	$k^6 B_2(k)$	DV	DV
	$f_{\text{NL}}^{1,3,4,5}(k)$	DV	DV
	$f_{\text{NL}}^2(k)$	DV	DV
RHM	$k^6 B_{1,3,4,5}(k)$	CV	DV
	$k^6 B_2(k)$	DV	DV
	$f_{\text{NL}}^{1,3,4,5}(k)$	DV	DV
	$f_{\text{NL}}^2(k)$	DV	DV
RSET	$k^6 B_{1,3,4,5}(k)$	CV	DV
	$k^6 B_2(k)$	DV	DV
	$f_{\text{NL}}^{1,3,4,5}(k)$	DV	DV
	$f_{\text{NL}}^2(k)$	DV	DV
FIC	$k^6 B_{1,3,4,5}(k)$	CV	DV
	$k^6 B_2(k)$	CV	DV
	$f_{\text{NL}}^{1,3,4,5}(k)$	CV	DV
	$f_{\text{NL}}^2(k)$	CV	DV

TABLE VI. Asymptotic developments of usual quantum initial conditions in Contaldi's formalism and classical Frozen Initial Curvature ones.

Initial Condition	Limit	C_k	D_k
BD	0	$\frac{1}{\sqrt{8k}} \left(\frac{1}{k\eta t}\right)^2 + o(k^{-\frac{5}{2}})$	$C_k + o(k^{-\frac{5}{2}})$
	$+\infty$	$-\frac{1}{\sqrt{2k}} e^{-ik\eta t} + o(k^{-\frac{1}{2}})$	$0 + o\left(\frac{1}{k\eta t}\right)^{1/2}$
HD	0	$(1+i)\sqrt{\frac{\eta t}{8}} \left(\frac{1}{k\eta t}\right)^2 + o(k^{-2})$	$C_k + o(k^{-2})$
	$+\infty$	$-\frac{1}{\sqrt{2k}} e^{-ik\eta t} + o(k^{-\frac{1}{2}})$	$0 + o(k^{-\frac{1}{2}})$
RHM	0	$-\frac{4i}{\pi} \sqrt{\frac{\pi\eta t}{32}} \left(\frac{1}{k\eta t}\right)^2 + o(k^{-2})$	$C_k + o(k^{-2})$
	$+\infty$	$\frac{e^{i\pi/4}}{\sqrt{2k}} e^{-\frac{3i}{2}k\eta t} + o(k^{-\frac{1}{2}})$	$0 + o(k^{-\frac{1}{2}})$
RSET	0	$\frac{i}{\sqrt{8k}} \frac{1}{k\eta t} + o(k^{-\frac{3}{2}})$	$C_k + o(k^{-\frac{3}{2}})$
	$+\infty$	$C_k + o(k^{-\frac{1}{2}})$	$0 + o(k^{-\frac{1}{2}})$
FIC	0	$-\sqrt{\frac{3}{2}} \frac{R^{(0)}}{4} + o(1)$	$C_k + o(1)$
	$+\infty$	$R^{(0)} \sqrt{\frac{3}{2}} \sqrt{\frac{4}{\pi k\eta t}} e^{i\pi/4} e^{-i\frac{k\eta t}{2}} + o(k^{-\frac{1}{2}})$	$R^{(0)} \sqrt{\frac{3}{2}} \sqrt{\frac{4}{\pi k\eta t}} e^{-i\pi/4} e^{3i\frac{k\eta t}{2}} + o(k^{-\frac{1}{2}})$

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